

The Ramirez Dwarf Cichlid Identified¹

By courtesy of the authors, we are enabled to quote from a scientific article by Dr. G. S. Myers and Mr. R. R. Harry, in which they describe and name the new and popular "Ramirezi" Cichlid. They propose for it the name *Apistogramma ramirezi*, thus utilizing the specific name informally given to this fish by Mr. Herman Blass, of Miami, Florida, who brought the fish from Venezuela.

"Most closely related to *Apistogramma ornatipinna* Ahl, and *A. ritense* (Haseman), from which it differs strongly in having 9² (versus 6) soft anal rays. It is a very deep-bodied species, with the snout bluntly rounded and shorter than the eye. Lower jaw slightly shorter than upper when mouth is closed. Rictus not reaching vertical of front margin of eye. Dorsal fin remarkably high, mostly in adult males, in which the black third spine and its greatly elongated and attenuated black lappet of fin-membrane form an important diagnostic character."

The authors proceed to say that the fish is described principally from an "adult male . . . collected by Manuel Vicente Ramirez and Herman Blass in April, 1947, and presented to us by Mr. William T. Innes. The fish were ob-

tained during a 500-mile auto trip south across the Llanos from Palenque, Venezuela. Mr. Blass does not know the names of any of the rivers crossed or of the large one at which they turned back, which was probably the Rio Meta. Nor does he know in what river they obtained this fish. However it is evidently from one of the tributaries of the Rio Apuré or Rio Meta in the states of Guárico, Portuguesa, or Apuré. While the indefiniteness of the type locality is most unfortunate, the fauna of these rivers is very similar, and the species probably occurs in both the Meta and the Apuré systems."

The authors wish us to point out the confusion likely to occur when non-scientists attempt to give scientific names to animals. They say: "It is only luck that the name *ramirezi*, given to this fish by Mr. Blass, is preserved. It might just as well have turned out to be a known species, already named. He published no scientific description or comparison of his fish, showing its differences from the others of its genus already known to science. We accept and perpetuate the specific name *ramirezi* for the fish chiefly because it has become popularly known to aquarists and to avoid confusion."

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This article must constitute the original description of *Apistogramma ramirezi* Myers and Harry, as the intended original description from which this is an abstract (not actually a quote) did not appear until August, 1948.

The complete description entitled "*Apistogramma ramirezi*, a Cichlid fish from Venezuela," by George S. Myers and Robert R. Harry, appeared in the Proceedings of the California Zoological Club, volume 1, number 1, pages 1-8, table 1.

2

The count of 9 soft anal rays is an error. The count should be 8.

R.R.H.